

Additional Material of the publication “Environmental Life Cycle Assessment of a Stilted and Vertical Bifacial Crop-Based Agrivoltaic Multi Land-Use System and Comparison with a Mono Land-Use of Agricultural Land”

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Short overview of yield reduction in APV-plants:

One factor that influences the ability of a crop to grow under partial shade is the light saturation point. For some plants only a small part of the available sunlight is needed to reach the maximum rate of photosynthesis [1], which makes them suitable for APV-systems, while others have a high radiation demand (e.g., C4 plants) [2]. Beck et al. [2] divided a large number of crops in three categories to represent how their yield is expected to change under shaded conditions: (1) positive effects are dominant, which leads to a higher yield (e.g., potatoes, salad or spinach); (2) no significant changes; hence equal yield is expected (e.g., rape, rye, oats); and (3) negative effects dominate, which expectedly decreases yields (e.g., corn, wheat, horticulture). Nevertheless, this evaluation is based on experiments under an existing ground mounted PV plant and therefore cannot simply be transferred to other APV systems. For example, the yield of winter wheat, which is expected to decrease based on the categorization of Beck et al. [2], was found to increase in an APV-system by Weselek et al. [3] in dry and hot conditions compared to an open field production. At the same moment also decreases up to 50% were found in agroforestry systems depending on factors such as shading intensity and time of shading in the plant growth period [4, 5].

Table S1. Overview of used machinery with working width and diesel consumption for every crop and scenario, respectively. Working width and diesel consumption based on data from KTBL [6].

Operation	Machinery	Crop	Scenario	Working width [m]	Diesel consumption [l ha ⁻¹]		
					median	min	max
tillage, ploughing	4-furrow-plough	sugar beet, winter wheat, soybean	VB, S, Agri	1.40	27.06	26.81	28.84
tillage, harrowing	spring tine harrow	sugar beet, soybean	VB, S, Agri	7.40	6.57	6.14	7.22
tillage, chiseling	chisel plough	winter wheat	VB, S, Agri	9.50	9.82	9.07	10.91
tillage, currying	weeder	winter wheat, soybean	VB, S	6.90	2.60	2.43	2.83
			Agri	23.00	2.92	2.57	3.38
sowing	sowing machine	sugar beet	VB, S	6.00	3.75	3.54	4.05
			Agri	9.00	4.29	3.95	4.54
		VB, S, Agri	9.00	4.19	3.62	4.72	
hoeing	hoeing roller	sugar beet	VB, S	6.00	3.75	3.59	4.02

			Agri	9.00	3.98	3.67	4.28	
fertilising	broadcaster	sugar beet, winter wheat, soybean	VB	10.00	0.97	0.93	1.01	
			S	12.00	0.97	0.93	1.01	
			Agri	36.00	1.08	1.04	1.15	
liquid manure spreading	vacuum tanker (application close to the ground)	sugar beet, winter wheat, soybean	Agri	24.00	6.90	6.44	7.42	
solid manure spreading	hydraulic loader and spreader	sugar beet, winter wheat, soybean	Agri	12.00	8.51	8.46	8.80	
application of plant protection	field sprayer	sugar beet, winter wheat, soybean	VB	10.00	1.01	0.95	1.06	
			S	12.00	1.01	0.95	1.06	
			Agri	24.00	1.24	1.06	1.36	
harvesting	complete harvester	sugar beet	VB, S, Agri	3.00	39.13	37.49	40.93	
	combine harvester	winter wheat	VB, S	8.50	23.21	22.36	24.98	
				Agri	9.90	23.68	21.99	25.35
		soybean	VB, S, Agri	7.00	26.95	24.36	30.06	
mowing of flower strip	Mower	/	VB, S	1.90	26.78	26.02	27.88	

Table S2. Fertilizer amount, distribution into fertilizer types and distribution of nutrients within the different fertilizer types

Crop	Fertilizer type (N/P ₂ O ₅ /K ₂ O)	Fertilizer amount [kg]	N [kg]	P ₂ O ₅ [kg]	K ₂ O [kg]
sugar beet	Calcium ammonium nitrate (27/0/0)	121.00	32.67	/	/
	Urea (46/0/0)	150.00	69.00	/	/
	Potassium chloride (0/0/60)	283.40	/	/	170.04
	Diammonphosphat (18/46/0)	185.00	33.30	85.10	/
	Green manure	/	20.00	/	/
Total		739.40	154.97	85.10	170.04
winter wheat	Calcium ammonium nitrate (27/0/0)	151.00	40.77	/	/
	Urea (46/0/0)	180.00	82.80	/	/
	Potassium chloride (0/0/60)	50.00	/	/	30.00
	Diammonphosphat (18/46/0)	119.50	21.51	54.97	/
Total		500.5	145.08	54.97	30.00
soybean	Calcium ammonium nitrate (27/0/0)	31.60	14.54	/	/
	Potassium chloride (0/0/60)	83.40	/	/	50.04
	Diammonphosphat (18/46/0)	141.40	25.45	65.04	/
	Green manure	/	20.00	/	/
Total		256.40	59.99	65.04	50.04

Table S3. Overview of used emission models for calculation of diverse field emissions

Field emission	Emission model	Reference
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Nitrous oxide (N ₂ O)	IPCC 2019 Tier 2 with country specific data	[7-9]
Ammonia (NH ₃)	EMEP/EEA 2019 Tier 2 with country specific data	[8-10]
Nitrogen oxides (NO _x)	EMEP/EEA 2019 Tier 1	[10]
Nitrate (NO ₃ ⁻)	SALCA-Nitrate with country specific data	[11, 12]
Phosphate & Phosphorus	SALCA-Phosphorus with country specific data	[12, 13]
Heavy metals	SALCA-Heavy Metals with country specific data	[12, 14]
Carbon dioxide	IPCC 2006 Tier 1	[15]
Particulate matter (PM _{2.5})	EMEP/EEA 2019 Tier 2	[10]

Table S1. Life Cycle Inventory of the production of sugar beet, winter wheat and soybean, respectively in the S- and VB-APV scenario

Input/ Output Flow	Sugar beet				Winter wheat				Soybean				
	Uncertainty	mean	Unit	SD*	Uncertainty	mean	Unit	SD*	Uncertainty	mean	Unit	SD*	
Inputs	application of plant protection	logarithmic normal	5.67E-05	ha	1.00	logarithmic normal	1.77E-04	ha	1.00	logarithmic normal	4.96E-04	ha	1.07
	fertilising	logarithmic normal	5.15E-05	ha	1.00	logarithmic normal	7.09E-04	ha	1.00	logarithmic normal	3.62E-04	ha	1.07
	green manure	logarithmic normal	1.20E-05	ha	1.00					logarithmic normal	2.45E-04	ha	1.07
	harvesting, by complete harvester	logarithmic normal	1.29E-05	ha	1.00								
	combine harvesting					logarithmic normal	1.77E-04	ha	1.00	logarithmic normal	3.62E-04	ha	1.07
	hoeing	logarithmic normal	2.58E-05	ha	1.00								
	sowing	logarithmic normal	1.29E-05	ha	1.00	logarithmic normal	1.77E-04	ha	1.00	logarithmic normal	3.62E-04	ha	1.07
	sugar beet seed	logarithmic normal	2.52E-05	kg	1.00								
	wheat seed					logarithmic normal	3.42E-02	kg	1.00				
	soybean seed									logarithmic normal	6.13E-02	ha	1.07
	tillage, harrowing	logarithmic normal	2.58E-05	ha	1.00	logarithmic normal	1.77E-04	ha	1.00	logarithmic normal	3.62E-04	ha	1.07
	tillage, ploughing	logarithmic normal	1.29E-05	ha	1.00	logarithmic normal	1.77E-04	ha	1.00	logarithmic normal	3.62E-04	ha	1.07

tillage, chisseling		logarithmic normal	1.77E-04 ha	1.00	
tillage, currying		logarithmic normal	1.77E-04 ha	1.00	logarithmic normal 3.62E-04 ha 1.07
transport	3.00E-03 t*km		t*k 3.00E-03 m		3.00E-03 t*km
calcium ammonium nitrate	1.67E-03 kg		2.68E-02 kg		
diammonium phosphate	2.56E-03 kg		2.12E-02 kg		5.12E-02 kg
potassium chloride	3.92E-03 kg		8.87E-03 kg		3.02E-02 kg
urea	2.08E-03 kg		3.19E-02 kg		1.14E-02 kg
Out-puts					
Sugar beet	9.30E-01 kg				
Winter wheat			1.06E+00 kg		
Soybean					9.41E-01 kg
Particulates, < 2.5 um	2.99E-06 kg		2.74E-05 kg		3.46E-05 kg
Ammonia, to air	triangular min=2.11E-04 mode=4.22E-04 max=6.34E-04 kg	triangular	min=2.70E-03 mode=5.41E-03 max=8.11E-03 kg	triangular	min=2.23E-03 mode=4.46E-03 max=6.69E-03 kg
Carbon dioxide, fossil from lime fertilization, to air	uniform min=9.14E-05 max=1.83E-04 kg	uniform	min=2.51E-02 max=5.02E-02 kg		
Carbon dioxide, fossil from urea fertilization, to air	uniform min=1.63E-03 kg	uniform	min=1.46E-03 kg	uniform	min=9.00E-03 max=1.80E-02 kg

		max=3.26E-03	max=2.92E-03	
Dinitrogen monoxide, direct, to air	triangular	min=4.42E-06 mode=7.58E-05 max=1.93E-04 kg	min=4.28E-05 mode=9.71E-04 max=1.02E-03 kg	min=3.80E-05 mode=4.96E-04 max=1.10E-03 kg
Dinitrogen monoxide, indirect volatilisation, to air	triangular	min=3.37E-07 mode=1.69E-06 max=3.03E-06 kg	min=4.04E-06 mode=2.16E-05 max=3.64E-05 kg	min=3.42E-06 mode=1.71E-05 max=3.07E-05 kg
Dinitrogen monoxide, indirect leaching, to air	triangular	min=0.00E0 mode=1.26E-05 max=3.25E-05 kg	min=0.00E0 mode=1.63E-4 max=1.72E-04 kg	min=0.00E0 mode=8.27E-5 max=1.85E-04 kg
Nitrogen oxides, to air	triangular	min=1.07E-05 mode=8.58E-05 max=2.23E-04 kg	min=1.29E-04 mode=1.03E-03 max=2.68E-03 kg	min=1.09E-04 mode=8.69E-04 max=2.26E-03 kg
Cadmium, to soil		1.11E-07 kg	9.79E-07 kg	2.61E-06 kg
Chromium, to soil		2.82E-07 kg	1.83E-06 kg	5.82E-06 kg
Copper, to soil		-1.09E-06 kg	3.30E-07 kg	-3.67E-06 kg
Lead, to soil		-3.32E-08 kg	2.62E-07 kg	4.26E-07 kg
Mercury, to soil		-8.09E-09 kg	2.67E-10 kg	
Nickel, to soil		-3.64E-08 kg	1.52E-06 kg	-8.86E-07 kg

Zinc, to soil	-5.65E-06 kg	-4.99E-06 kg	-8.72E-06 kg
Cadmium, ion, to ground water	6.75E-10 kg	8.52E-09 kg	1.74E-08 kg
Chromium, ion, to ground water	2.89E-07 kg	3.66E-06 kg	7.50E-06 kg
Copper, ion, to ground water	4.59E-08 kg	4.43E-07 kg	9.75E-07 kg
Lead, to ground water	6.68E-09 kg	5.46E-08 kg	5.64E-08 kg
Mercury, to ground water	1.71E-11 kg	1.13E-10 kg	
Nitrate, to ground water	1.96E-04 kg		-1.41E-02 kg
Nitrate, to ground water, soybean as previous crop		1.62E-02 kg	
Nitrate, to ground water, sugar beet as previous crop		1.06E-02 kg	
Phosphate, to ground water	9.69E-07 kg	1.24E-05 kg	2.54E-05 kg
Zinc, ion, to ground water	4.32E-07 kg	4.66E-06 kg	9.24E-06 kg
Cadmium, ion, to surface water	1.83E-13 kg	1.36E-12 kg	3.88E-12 kg
Chromium, ion, to surface water	2.22E-11 kg	1.66E-10 kg	4.75E-10 kg
Copper, ion, to surface water	1.83E-11 kg	1.04E-10 kg	3.20E-10 kg
Lead, to surface water	1.28E-11 kg	6.16E-11 kg	8.91E-11 kg
Mercury, to surface water	1.24E-13 kg	4.84E-13 kg	
Nickel, ion, to surface water	2.05E-11 kg	1.40E-10 kg	4.21E-10 kg
Phosphate, to surface water	2.94E-06 kg	3.53E-05 kg	7.37E-05 kg
Phosphorus, to surface water	8.90E-10 kg	6.71E-09 kg	1.92E-10 kg
Zinc, ion, to surface water	4.39E-11 kg	2.78E-10 kg	7.74E-10 kg

*SD...standard deviation

Figure S1. Contribution analysis of the Terrestrial Ecotoxicity of all assessed scenarios; error bars show the 5% and 95% interpercentile range of indicator's probability distribution function, based on 1,000 Monte Carlo runs; lower-case characters represent significant differences.

Figure S2. Contribution analysis of Fine Particulate Matter Formation of all assessed scenarios; error bars show the 5% and 95% interpercentile range of indicator's probability distribution function, based on 1,000 Monte Carlo runs; lower-case characters represent significant differences.

Figure S3. Contribution analysis of Fossil Resource Scarcity of all assessed scenarios; error bars show the 5% and 95% interpercentile range of indicator's probability distribution function, based on 1,000 Monte Carlo runs; lower-case characters represent significant differences.

Table S5. Life cycle impact assessment results of all studied scenarios for all assessed impact categories including the 5th and 95th percentile

Scenario	Value	CC	HCT	HNCT	TE	FE	TA	FPMF	MRS	FRS
		g CO ₂ eq.	g 1,4-DCB	g 1,4-DCB	kg 1,4-DCB	mg P eq.	g SO ₂ eq.	g PM _{2.5} eq.	g Cu eq.	g oil eq.
S-APV	Median	114.09	61.83	328.73	1.26	45.56	0.64	0.24	2.59	26.84
	5 th percentile	95.05	36.80	214.02	0.78	26.26	0.56	0.21	2.32	22.81
	95 th percentile	149.90	116.33	741.54	2.78	98.30	0.77	0.32	2.96	34.26
	95 th percentile	149.90	116.33	741.54	2.78	98.30	0.77	0.32	2.96	34.26
VB-APV	Median	61.41	18.49	227.68	1.22	21.22	0.48	0.15	1.73	13.59
	5 th percentile	49.34	11.02	144.54	0.68	12.36	0.42	0.13	1.55	11.08
	95 th percentile	84.14	37.84	505.82	3.05	42.49	0.56	0.19	2.01	18.05
	95 th percentile	84.14	37.84	505.82	3.05	42.49	0.56	0.19	2.01	18.05
Agri-green	Median	28.32	15.35	161.03	1.15	12.86	0.22	0.08	1.37	6.58
	5 th percentile	25.39	8.81	109.59	0.61	8.06	0.20	0.07	1.15	5.76
	95 th percentile	31.81	28.94	295.11	2.74	23.71	0.26	0.09	1.61	7.48
	95 th percentile	31.81	28.94	295.11	2.74	23.71	0.26	0.09	1.61	7.48
Agri-AUT	Median	167.63	16.28	220.49	0.44	71.65	0.36	0.12	0.47	53.29
	5 th percentile	163.85	8.30	115.29	0.31	34.60	0.34	0.11	0.42	48.44
	95 th percentile	172.76	76.85	952.97	0.77	167.33	0.39	0.13	0.53	59.04
	95 th percentile	172.76	76.85	952.97	0.77	167.33	0.39	0.13	0.53	59.04
PV	Median	83.87	18.19	270.28	1.10	29.78	0.48	0.19	2.00	18.87
	5 th percentile	65.01	11.14	163.19	0.61	17.12	0.39	0.15	1.65	14.88
	95 th percentile	113.56	39.11	628.73	2.81	64.74	0.58	0.24	2.45	24.86
	95 th percentile	113.56	39.11	628.73	2.81	64.74	0.58	0.24	2.45	24.86

Table S6. Change of impacts in % for both S- and VB-APV scenario when producing PV-module and inverter in Europe; green colour indicates a decrease in impact or an increase below 1%, yellow an increase between 1-5%, orange an increase between 5-10% and red an increase >10%

Impact category	Scenario	Change of impact		
		PV-module [%]	Inverter [%]	whole APV plant [%]
CC	S-APV	-35.47%	-20.46%	-18.39%
	VB-APV	-36.69%	-17.86%	-22.35%
HCT	S-APV	-11.22%	-2.02%	-1.46%
	VB-APV	-14.32%	-1.78%	+2.64%
HNCT	S-APV	-5.75%	-4.14%	-4.67%
	VB-APV	+3.43%	+1.12%	+1.77%
TE	S-APV	-0.66%	-0.39%	-0.19%
	VB-APV	-0.50%	+5.37%	+4.30%
FE	S-APV	+47.20%	+13.82%	+19.45%
	VB-APV	+46.07%	+9.24%	+22.88%
TA	S-APV	-34.78%	-10.44%	-14.13%
	VB-APV	-33.12%	-8.07%	-10.64%
FPMF	S-APV	-32.35%	-12.02%	-15.08%
	VB-APV	-31.38%	-9.14%	-13.78%
MRS	S-APV	-3.97%	+1.18%	-1.95%
	VB-APV	-1.07%	+2.23%	+1.23%
FRS	S-APV	-21.98%	-13.67%	-10.80%
	VB-APV	-23.12%	-11.18%	-13.70%

What can be clearly seen by the colour indication that for the majority a decrease in impacts can be obtained. Major decreases are possible in CC, TA, FPMF and FRS for both PV-module and inverter production and consequentially for the total impact of the APV plant due to the lower impact of the European electricity and heat mix and in some impact categories due to shorter transport distances and different modes (only lorry instead of ship and lorry).

In HCT, HNCT, TE and MRS there is partially a minor increase in impacts, while in FE a major increase can be obtained. This is for all impact categories except for TE due to the reason that when using the lignite-containing European electricity mix there is also an increase of need of treatment of spoil from lignite mining. Outputs in this process have an enormous standard deviation, which leads to higher median values than when producing in China. In TE the longer transport with lorry leads to an increase of treatment of brake wear emissions, which again has a high standard deviation for outputs. The increase in FE is due to higher long-term Phosphate emissions to the ground-water when electricity is generated by lignite than from hard coal. It must be taken into account that these results could change if the production site is located in a country with no electricity produced from lignite.

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